

BRAND PREFERENCE OF CAR USERS **Dr. T. Jebasheela* & Dr. H. Christy Cynthia****

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Abstract:

A Brand is name, item, symbol or design, or a combination of them which is intended to identify the goods or services of one seller or a group of seller and to differentiate them from those of competitors. For example Santo TATA indicia, Wagon R etc are brands. Branding is the management process by which a product is branded. It is a general term covering various activities such as giving a brand name to a product. Designing a brand mark and establishing and popularizing it. The importance of branding arose mainly because of the over emphasis on advertisement. It fact the brand name is mean for advertisement and also focused on educational level.

Introduction:

A Brand is name, item, symbol or design, or a combination of them which is intended to identify the goods or services of one seller or a group of seller and to differentiate them from those of competitors. For example Santo TATA indicia, Wagon R etc are brands. Branding is the management process by which a product is branded. It is a general term covering various activities such as giving a brand name to a product. Designing a brand mark and establishing and popularizing it. The importance of branding arose mainly because of the over emphasis on advertisement. It fact the brand name is mean for advertisement and also focused on educational level.

Scope of the Study:

The scope of the study has a clear knowledge about the consumer's preference towards four wheelers. The present study covers only cars since the market is flooded with a wide choice of models. In fact that, the fortunes of the four wheelers industry have turned a full circle and it is now facing with a stance in demand situation. A natural corollary of this should be a cut in prices. But this has not happened because of the shift in consumer preference for more sophisticated models irrespective of the prices. In such a situation this study is totally relevant and this study also helps to understand the factors which influence the preference of the consumers towards cars. This study covers brand preference of car users in Sivakasi.

Objectives of the Study:

The objectives of the study are

- ✓ To examine the brand preference of cars among consumers.
- ✓ To analyze the influencing factor of purchasing car.

Sampling Design:

The population of the study is large in number. So the researcher is decided to use Convenient Sampling Method to collect 80 respondents

Sex Wise Classification:

As sex is an important element to make the person purchase, a product, the researcher has taken sex – wise classification for this study. The number of respondents select for his study is 80. Out of which 59 were male and the rest were females. Male respondents are again classified into professionals and business people. Female respondents are classified into housewife and professionals. The classification of respondents according to sex is displayed in the Table 1.

Table 1: Sex Wise Classification

S.No	Particulars	No. of Respondents	Percentage of Total (%)
1	Male	52	65.0
2	Female	28	35.0
Total		80	100

Source: Primary Data

It is evident from the Table 1 that, Majority of the respondents belongs to male category, their share being 65% of the total respondents. Females occupy only 35% of the respondents. It is inferred that Majority of the respondents (65.0%) are Male.

Nature of the Job: The occupation of the respondents plays a decisive role in choosing a particular brand of cars. The selected respondents have been analyzed on the basis of the nature of occupation and results are presented in the Table 2.

Table 2: Nature of the Job

S.No	Particulars	No. of Respondents	Percentage of Total (%)
1	Government	22	27.5
2	Private	32	40.0
3	Business	26	32.5
Total		80	100

Source: Primary Data

Table 2 clearly shows that out of 80 sample respondents, 40% of them are private employees, 32.5% of them are business people and the remaining 27.5% are government employees. It is evident that a Most of the respondents (40.0%) are private employees.

Income Wise Classification:

Apart from the educational level and occupation, the family income plays a dominant role in making a purchase decision. Consumers spending depend upon the quantum of family income. Families which are having more income would be able to spend more than the families who have less income. Hence, the monthly income of the sample respondents has been collected and represented in the Table 3.

Table 3: Income Wise Classification

S.No	Particulars	No. of Respondents	Percentage of Total (%)
1	Below Rs.10,000	3	3.8
2	Rs.10,001 to Rs.20000	16	20.0
3	Rs.20,001 to Rs.30,000	41	51.2
4	Above Rs.30,001	20	25.0
Total		80	100.0

Source: Primary Data

It is quite evident from the Table 3 shows that, 51.2% of the respondents are coming under the category of family income ranging between Rs.20,001 and Rs.30,000, 20.0% of the respondents are coming under the category of family income Rs.10,001 to Rs.20,000, 25% of the respondents are coming under the category of family income above Rs.30,001 and only 3.8% of the respondents are having a family monthly income of less than Rs.10,000. On the whole it is found that Majority of the respondents (51.2%) are coming under the category of monthly income between Rs.20,000 to Rs.30000 in the study area.

Brand Preference of Cars:

The consumer's brand preference is differs one person to another. The brand preference of consumers have been analyzed and presented in the Table 4.

Table 4: Brand Preference of car users

S.No	Particulars	No. of Respondents	Percentage of Total (%)
1	Honda	13	16.2
2	Ford	16	20.0
3	Hyundai	2	2.5
4	Chevrolet	5	6.2
5	Tata	1	1.2
6	Maruti Suzuki	25	31.2
7	Renault	2	2.5
8	Volkswagen	6	7.5
9	BMW	7	8.8
10	Toyota	3	3.8
Total		80	100.0

Source: Primary Data

Table 4 it is clearly found the fact that most of the respondents 31.2% are using the Maruti Suzuki cars followed by Ford 20.0% and Honda 16.2%. It is evident that Most of the respondents 31.2% are using the Maruti Suzuki.

Factors Influencing Purchase Decision:

The researcher has made an attempt in the study area to ascertain the person behind the decision to buy a car. The facts collected are presented in the Table 5.

Table 5: Factors Influencing Purchase Decision

S.No	Particulars	No. of Respondents	Percentage of Total (%)
1	Family	38	47.5
2	Own Decision	18	22.5
3	Spouse	14	17.5
4	Friend	6	7.5
5	Mechanic	2	2.5

6	Dealer	2	2.5
Total		80	100

Source: Primary Data

Table 5 reveals that nearly 47.5% of the respondents have been influenced by the family in making their decisions, 22.5% were influenced by own decision, 17.5% of the respondents by spouse, 7.5% of the respondents were influenced by friend, 2.5% of the respondents were influenced by dealer and the remaining 2.5% of the respondents were influenced by mechanic. It is found for the study area that family plays a dominant role in making purchase decisions for a car.

Chi Square Test:

A chi-square test, also referred to as χ^2 test is any statistical hypothesis test in which the sampling distribution of the test statistic is a chi-square distribution when the null hypothesis is true. Chi-squared tests are often constructed from a sum of squared errors, or through the sample variance. A chi-squared test can then be used to reject the null hypothesis that the data are independent.

Formula:

$$\chi^2 = \sum \frac{(o - e)^2}{e}$$

χ^2	The chi-square test statistic
O	Observed count or frequency
E	Expected count or frequency
N	Total number of observations
RT	Row total
CT	Column total

The researcher has used chi-square test by using SPSS.

Hypothesis:

There is no significant relationship between income of the respondents and reasons for purchase car.

Table 6: Relationship between Income and Reason for Purchasing Car

			Reason for purchase of car				Total
			To Maintain Status	For Necessity	For Comfort Travel	For Distance Travel	
Income	Below Rs.10,000	Count	3	0	0	0	3
		% within income	100.00%	0.00%	0.00%	0.00%	100.00%
		% within why purchase car	15.80%	0.00%	0.00%	0.00%	3.80%
		% of Total	3.80%	0.00%	0.00%	0.00%	3.80%
	Rs.10,000 to Rs.20000	Count	8	18	9	6	41
		% within income	19.50%	43.90%	22.00%	14.60%	100.00%
		% within why purchase car	42.10%	58.10%	40.90%	75.00%	51.20%
		% of Total	10.00%	22.50%	11.20%	7.50%	51.20%
	Rs. 20,001 to 30,000	Count	6	5	9	0	20
		% within income	30.00%	25.00%	45.00%	0.00%	100.00%
		% within why purchase car	31.60%	16.10%	40.90%	0.00%	25.00%
		% of Total	7.50%	6.20%	11.20%	0.00%	25.00%
	Above Rs. 30,000	Count	2	8	4	2	16
		% within income	12.50%	50.00%	25.00%	12.50%	100.00%
		% within why purchase car	10.50%	25.80%	18.20%	25.00%	20.00%
		% of Total	2.50%	10.00%	5.00%	2.50%	20.00%
Total	Count	19	31	22	8	80	
	% within income	23.80%	38.80%	27.50%	10.00%	100.00%	
	% within why purchase car	100.00%	100.00%	100.00%	100.00%	100.00%	
	% of Total	23.80%	38.80%	27.50%	10.00%	100.00%	

Table 7: Chi-Square Tests

	Value	Df	Asymp. Sig. (2-sided)
Pearson Chi-Square	18.606 ^a	9	0.029
Likelihood Ratio	19.414	9	0.022
Linear-by-Linear Association	0.819	1	0.365
N of Valid Cases	80		

a. 10 cells (62.5%) have expected count less than 5. The minimum expected count is .30.

Source: Computed Data

Result: The calculated value (0.029) is more than the table value. So, the null hypothesis is accepted. There is no significant relationship between income of the respondents and reasons for purchase car.

Conclusion:

There are roughly 150 new car models on the market today, many of the only narrowly distinguishable from each other. The sedans are flames surface affairs with elongated rooflines, and even the sporty coupes rely

on huge grilles to trumpet their brand lineage. Most emit the same muffled calls, so you can't reliably classify them by sound, either. This guide is intended to help you identify the 10 cars that, through a rare combination of strengths, stand apart. They reward close observation. We hope the following pages will tune you in to the attributes that mark the differentiation. Individual areas of noteworthiness are called out, but the assembled cars share the following traits: They cost less than \$80,000, they excel at delivering value for the money, they have a strong mastery of their segment, and they are graceful in motion the brand and model of the car is change in day to day. So the researcher concluded that the desire and buying behavior and brand preference of the car users will be change.

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